

Morphological Study of Branching Pattern External Carotid Artery in Carotid Triangle

Kamal D. Pawar^{#1}, Ashwini Rajeev Desai^{2(*)}, Rajeev Raghunathrao Desai³.

¹Tutor, Department of Anatomy, DRBVP Rural Medical College, Loni, Maharashtra. India.

(*) Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, Zydus Medical College and Hospital, Dahod. Gujarat.

³Professor, Department of Anatomy, Zydus Medical College and Hospital, Dahod. Gujarat.

ABSTRACT

External carotid artery is the main artery of head, neck and face. The branches of external carotid artery are key landmarks for exposure and appropriate placement of cross-clamps on the carotid artery during endarterectomy. The knowledge of branching pattern of external carotid artery is important to minimize postoperative complications in neck and face surgeries. This study aimed to explore the variation in branching pattern of external carotid artery and origin of each branch in carotid triangle. One hundred sixty hemi-sections (80 cadavers) of head and neck of either sex were utilized for this study. The level of bifurcation of common carotid artery were noted. The branching pattern of external carotid artery in carotid triangle were observed for variations. Normal level of bifurcation of common carotid artery was observed in 110 (68.75%), higher level in 34(21.25%) and lower level in 16(10%) of the hemi sections. The most common variation in branching pattern of external carotid artery was, common linguofacial trunk in 12(7.5%) and its incidence was more on right side than the left. Present study observed that, whenever there was origin of ascending pharyngeal artery in the form of occipito-pharyngeal trunk (in 5 hemi sections), it was always at lower level than the origin of facial artery. Present study observed multiple variations like origin of superior thyroid artery from common carotid artery, origin of superior laryngeal artery from external carotid in one hemi-sections. Early division of external carotid artery was observed in 2 hemi-sections (1.25%). It has been found that the branching pattern of external carotid artery has great variations. The anatomical knowledge of variations of these vessels is necessary for the surgeons while doing head and neck surgeries.

Key words: *Common carotid artery, Variations, Linguo-facial trunk, occipito-pharyngeal trunk, Neck surgeries.*

Introduction

The external carotid artery (ECA) is the major artery supplying head, neck and face regions. It arises from common carotid artery (CCA) at the level of upper border of thyroid cartilage. First it ascends little forward and then slightly backward and laterally midway between the angle of mandible and tip of mastoid process. Here it enters in the substance of parotid gland and terminate by dividing into maxillary and superficial temporal artery [1].

It has eight branches superior thyroid, lingual, facial, occipital, ascending pharyngeal, posterior auricular and superficial temporal and maxillary. The superior thyroid, lingual and facial arteries arise from anterior aspect. The occipital and posterior auricular arises from its posterior aspect and ascending pharyngeal artery arises from medial aspect. The superficial temporal and maxillary are the two terminal branches [2].

Out of eight, five branches of external carotid artery arise in the carotid triangle. The superior thyroid artery arises at the level just below the greater cornu of hyoid bone and the lingual artery arises opposite the tip of greater cornu of hyoid bone. The facial artery arises from anterior aspect, immediately above the greater cornu of hyoid bone and occipital artery arises from the posterior aspect opposite to the facia[1].

Though common carotid artery has no branches other than external and internal carotid arteries, occasionally it may give rise to the superior thyroid, inferior thyroid, vertebral, superior laryngeal or occipital artery. The external carotid may give rise common trunk of superior thyroid and lingual artery. Also, common lingo-facial trunk may arise from it [1]. Devdas D et al. observed 7.5% cases of accessory branches of external carotid artery such as accessory ascending pharyngeal artery, masseteric branches, superior laryngeal artery. They also observed a small branch to internal jugular vein and thyrolinguofacial trunk arising from external carotid artery [3].

Rao and Shetty in case report observed all eight branches of external carotid artery arose from common point just above the its origin. They further mentioned that the branches of external carotid artery are useful as a key landmark for dissection and catheterizations [4]. (Rao TR) It is also helpful in surgeries like tonsillectomy, laryngectomy, thyroidectomy and other surgeries of neck regions[5].

Study design: Descriptive study.

Sample size: The study was done on 160 hemi-sections of head and neck region of 80 adult human cadavers.

Sample size n = $Z^2pq/d^2 = 1.96 \times 1.96 \times 0.78 \times 0.22 / 0.1 \times 0.1 = 66.55$

$P = 78.95\% = 0.78$ From previous study³. $d = 10\%$

Material and Methods

The study was carried out in the Department of Anatomy, Rural Medical college, Loni. after approval of institutional ethical committee (Reg no- PIMS/DR/RMC/2020/338). The 160 hemi-sections of head and neck regions (80 adult human cadavers) which were dissected by undergraduate students in department of anatomy were utilized. The hemi sections with damaged carotid arteries were excluded. The carotid sheath was removed for proper visualization of the level of bifurcation of common carotid artery and its branches. The bifurcation of common carotid artery above the level of upper border of thyroid cartilage was noted as higher level and below the level, noted as lower level. Further the branches of external carotid artery in carotid triangle were traced and variations in the branching pattern were noted and photographs were taken wherever necessary. The data was tabulated and percentage of hemi section having variations in branching pattern of ECA in carotid triangle were computed and analyzed.

Results and Discussion

In present study out on 160 hemi section (Right 80 and left 80). Normal level of bifurcation of common carotid artery was observed in 110(68.75%), higher level in 34(21.25%) and lower level in 16(10%) hemi sections.

Table no1: Showing the number and percentage of different variations in branching pattern of external carotid artery.

Sr.N O.	Variations in branching pattern of external carotid artery	Right side- number (N=80) and percentage	Left side- Number (N=80) and percentage.	Total number (N=160) and percentage
1.	Superior thyroid artery arose from common carotid artery (Fig 1&2)	0	2 (2.5%)	2 (1.25%)
2.	Superior thyroid artery arose at carotid bifurcation. (Fig 4&9)	2(2.5%)	0	2(1.25%)
3.	Superior laryngeal artery arose from ECA. (Fig 1&6)	0	2(2.5%)	2(1.25%)
4.	Linguofacial trunk. (Fig 2,3,4&7)	9 (11.25%)	3(3.75%)	12 (7.5%)
5.	Ascending pharyngeal arose from the bifurcation of common carotid. (Fig 2)	0	1(1.25%)	1(0.63%)
6.	Ascending pharyngeal arose from internal carotid. (Fig10)	0	1(1.25%)	1(0.63%)
7.	Ascending pharyngeal arose at higher level from ECA. (Fig 1,4&5)	2(2.5%)	1(1.25%)	3(1.88%)
8.	Ascending pharyngeal artery arose at higher level as Occipito- pharyngeal trunk. (Fig 6,8&9)	3(3.75%)	2(2.5%)	5 (3.13%)
9.	Occipital artery origin at higher level as compared to facial. (Fig 5)	0	2(2.5%)	2(1.25%)
10.	Occipital artery arose at lower level as compared to facial. (Fig 1)	0	1(1.25%)	1(0.63%)
11.	Occipito auricular trunk. (Fig 4)	1(1.25%)	0	1(0.63%)
12.	Early division of external carotid artery. (Fig 3&7)	2(2.5%)	0	2(1.25%)

Fig 1: Left side hemisection showing bifurcation of common carotid artery at lower level with Superior thyroid artery(STA) arising from common carotid artery(CCA),Superior laryngeal artery(SLA) arises from external carotid artery(ECA) ,Ascending pharyngeal artery(APA) arising at higher level opposite to the Facial artery(FA), Occipital artery(OA) arises at the level Lingual artery (LA). Thyroid cartilage (TC).

Fig 2: Left side hemisection showing bifurcation of common carotid at higher level with Superior thyroid artery(STA) arising from common carotid artery(CCA), common Linguofacial trunk(LT), and Ascending pharyngeal artery(APA) arising at the point of bifurcation of common carotid artery, Internal carotid artery(ICA)

Fig 3: Right side hemi section showing common Linguofacial trunk(LFT), Ascending pharyngeal artery(APA), Superior thyroid artery(STA), Occipital artery(OA), External carotid artery (ECA)

Fig 4: Right side hemi section with superior thyroid artery(STA) arising from External carotid artery(ECA) at the level of bifurcation, Linguofacial Trunk (LFT), Occipito Auricular Trunk(OAT), high level of origin of Ascending Pharyngeal artery(APA), common carotid artery(CCA), External carotid artery(ECA), Internal carotid artery(ICA).

Fig 5: Right side hemi section with bifurcation of common carotid (CCA)at higher level, higher origin Ascending pharyngeal artery arise (APA) at the level of Facial artery(FA), Occipital artery (OA)also arise at higher level, External carotid artery(ECA), Superior thyroid artery(STA).

Fig 6: Left side hemisection with high level bifurcation of Common Carotid artery(CCA) showing Superior thyroid artery(STA), and superior laryngeal artery(SLA) arising from External carotid artery (ECA), Lingual artery(LA), Facial artery(FA) and Ascending pharyngeal artery(APA) arising from Occipitopharyngeal trunk(OPT).

Fig 7: Right side hemisection with high level division of common carotid artery (CCA) with immediate branching (Quadfurcation) of External carotid artery (ECA) showing Superior thyroid artery (STA), common Linguofacial trunk (LFT), Ascending pharyngeal artery (APA), Occipital artery (OA).

Fig 8: Left side hemisection showing Superior thyroid artery(STA), Lingual artery(LA), Facial artery(FA) and common Occipito-pharyngeal trunk(OPT), Occipital artery(OA), Ascending pharyngeal artery.

Fig 9: Right side hemi section showing Superior thyroid artery (STA) arising at the level of bifurcation, Lingual artery (LA), Facial artery (FA) and common Occipito-pharyngeal trunk (OPT).

Fig 10: Right side hemi section showing ascending pharyngeal artery (APA) arising from Internal carotid artery (ICA), Common carotid artery (CCA), External carotid artery (ECA), Superior thyroid artery(STA), Lingual artery(LA),

The knowledge of level of bifurcation of common carotid artery has clinical importance in pathogenesis of atheromatous diseases and also for its treatment by carotid stenting and Carotid endarterectomy [6]. The higher bifurcation of CCA may cause distal extension of plaque which may causes inadequate approaches for plaque removal and repairment surgery of artery [7].

Table no 2: Comparison table of level of bifurcation of common carotid artery.

Sr. No.	Researcher	Total number of Hemi-sections	Level of bifurcation of CCA(%)		
			Normal	High level	Low level
1	Lucev et al [8].	40	20(50%)	15(37.5%)	5(12.5%)
2	Ito et al [9].	80	46(57.5%)	25(31.2%)	9(11.3%)
3	Al-Rafiah et al [10].	60	29(48.4%)	28(46.6%)	3(5%)
4	Mompeo and Bajo [11].	38	24(63.15%)	14(36.85%)	0
5	Devdas D et al [3].	80	(60)75%	(20)25%	0
6	Present study	160	110(68.75%)	34(21.25%)	16(10%)

Many researchers studied the level of bifurcation and noted that higher level bifurcation was more common and lower-level bifurcation were less frequent [8-11]. According to some researchers the most common position of high-level bifurcation of CCA was at the level of hyoid bone [3,10].

In case of higher bifurcation of common carotid artery, during surgeries, surgeons should take precaution as there may be chances of damage to hypoglossal nerve and superior cervical sympathetic ganglion due to their close proximity and also keep in mind that in such case the superior thyroid artery may be arises from common carotid artery [12,13].

According to Rielly JP and Gulsen et al. variation of low-level carotid bifurcation appears to be a part of Klippel-Feil syndrome, a congenital anomaly manifested by fusion of cervical part of vertebral column [4,15]. In 2009, Murono et al. in case report observed the rare variation of non- bifurcation of common carotid artery on the right side. In this case, the common carotid artery continued as internal carotid artery and all branches in neck arose from internal carotid [16].

Adequate knowledge of variations in branching pattern of external carotid artery is necessary for preventing risk of iatrogenic bleeding during neck surgeries. It is also helpful for ligating arteries during head and neck surgeries and preventing complications during carotid endarterectomy [17].

Superior Thyroid Artery

In a cadaveric study of both sexes by Heltzel S et al. on left side out of 68, in 39 hemi sections superior thyroid artery arose from CCA and in 29 it arose from either carotid bifurcation or ECA. But on the right side out of 70 hemi sections it arose from CCA in 22 hemi sections and from carotid bifurcation or ECC in 47 hemi-sections. In one hemi section, they observed common thyro-lingual trunk. They further mentioned that there was difference in variation of branching pattern of ECA with regard to the side but not with the sex[5]. In present study it was observed that the origin of superior thyroid artery from CCA in two cases (2.5%) on left side (Fig. 1&2) and from carotid bifurcation in two cases (2.5%) on right side (Fig. 4&9).

Table no 3: Incidence of Superior thyroid artery originating from CCA.

Hollingshead et al. [2].	Banna et al [18].	Sanjeev et al [19]	A. Al-Rafiah et al [10]	Natsis et al [20].	Oval et al [21].	Present study
16%	10%	35.14%	18.3%	61%	5.88%	1.25%

Table no 4: Incidence of Superior thyroid artery from carotid bifurcation

Faller and Scharrer [22].	Quain [23].	Navakalyani et al[24].	Present study
36%	14%	8%	1.25%

In present study incidence of origin of superior thyroid artery from common carotid artery and from carotid bifurcation were less as compared to above reported studies [2,10,19,20,22,23]. Our observations of origin of superior thyroid artery from CCA were close to Oval et,al and the origin of superior thyroid artery from carotid bifurcation were close to the Navkalyani et al.[21,24].

Superior Laryngeal Artery

Superior laryngeal artery usually arises from superior thyroid artery but sometimes it directly arises from ECA. Anu VR reported its incidence in 32% of cases [17]. The knowledge of variations in origin and morphology of superior laryngeal artery is important during reconstructive surgery of larynx and during partial laryngectomy. Satheesha NB and Soumya KV reported rare variation with double superior laryngeal arteries with one as a branch from superior thyroid artery and other direct branch from external carotid artery[25]. In present study, in one hemi section there was lower level of bifurcation of common carotid artery with superior thyroid artery arose from common carotid artery and superior laryngeal arising from ECA (fig.1), in another hemi section on left side it arises from ECA between the origin of superior thyroid and lingual arteries(fig.6).

Linguofacial Trunk

Table no 5: Incidence of Linguofacial trunk

Lucev et al [8].	Yildrin et al [26].	Sanjeev et al [19]	Ozgur Z et al [27].	Al-Rafiah et al [10].	Oval et al [21].	Present study
20%	15%	18.92%	7.5%	1.7%	29.16%	7.5%

It is necessary for surgeons to differentiate between lingual and facial artery for accurate ligation of arteries during maxillofacial and oral surgeries [28]. After tonsillectomy, the most common site for formation of traumatic pseudoaneurysm is the linguofacial trunk [29]. Zumre et al. studied the variations in branching pattern of external carotid artery in human fetuses and observed linguofacial trunk in 20% ,thyo-lingual trunk in 2.5% and thyo-linguofacial in 2.5%[30]. According to Anil et al. incidence of linguofacial trunk was 10 to 20% of the cases[31]. Lappas et al observed linguofacial trunk in 14%[32]. In present study it was 7.5%,which was similar to Ozgur Z et al [27].

Ascending Pharyngeal Artery

Al-Rafiah et al. observed the variation in origin of ascending pharyngeal artery and reported that in 95% cases ascending pharyngeal artery arose from external carotid artery[10],in 3.3% from the carotid bifurcation and in 1.7% cases from internal carotid artery. They further noted that ascending pharyngeal artery arose by one root in 93.3% and by two roots in 6.7%. The prevalence of origin of ascending pharyngeal artery from internal carotid artery was 2% and 2.5% in studies of Hayashi et al and Zumre et al. respectively [7,30]. The present study observed origin of ascending pharyngeal artery from internal carotid artery in 0.63%(Fig10) which was close to Al-Rafiah et al(1.7%)[10]and Hyashi et al(2%)[7]. Origin of ascending pharyngeal from external carotid artery above the lingual artery is considered as higher origin and reported by Nakamasa and Thwin et al [33,28].

Occipital Artery

Occipital artery arose separately or arose as occipito-pharyngeal or occipito-auricular trunk. Hetzel et al. observed occipital artery frequently arose below the origin of facial artery in 68% and at or above the level of facial artery in 55%[5]. In present study occipital artery separately arose from ECA at higher level as compared to facial in 1.25% and at lower level in 0.63%.

Occipito-Pharyngeal Trunk

Table no 6: Incidence of Occipitopharyngeal trunk.

Hollingshead et al [2].	Anil et al [31].	Sanjeev et al [19].	Navakalyani et al [24].	Present study
14%	14%	24.32%	1%	3.13%

Present study observed that common occipito-pharyngeal trunk always arose at lower level than facial artery(Fig 6,8,9). Present study observations were close to Navakalyani et al[24].

Occipito-Auricular Trunk

The prevalence of occipito-auricular was 12.5% (Zumre et al), 18.3% (A.Al-Rafiah et al), 2.7% (Sanjeev et al), 2.5%(oval et al). The present study observations (0.63%) were close to Oval et,al.

Early Division of External Carotid Artery

Rao and Shetty during routine dissection observed a rare variation, where all eight branches arose close together from external carotid artery in carotid triangle just above the bifurcation of CCA and all except superior thyroid were crossed by hypoglossal nerve near their origins [4]. Such variation may predispose to iatrogenic injury to maxillary artery during parotid surgery and maxillofacial surgery [34]. Ogeng'o J A et al. mention this early division as Penta furcation and observed in 5.3% cases [35]. Lucev et al. reported its incidence in 12.5% cases [8.] Similar variation was also observed by Gluncic and colleagues [36]. In present study we observe early division of external carotid artery it in two hemi sections (2.5%) on right side (Fig 3&7).

Limitations

As study was conducted on already dissected hemi-sections of head and neck region, so we were unable to compare sex related differences.

Conclusion

The most common level of bifurcation of common carotid artery was at the level of upper border of thyroid cartilage in 68.75% followed by higher level in 21.25% and lower level in 10% and the most common variation in branching pattern of external carotid artery was linguofacial trunk. The study also observed that common occipito-pharyngeal trunk always arose at lower level than facial artery. The precise knowledge of bifurcation of common carotid artery and the variations in branching pattern of external carotid artery will be helpful in various diagnostic and therapeutic procedures and for proper ligation of arteries during head and neck surgeries to minimise the complication during surgeries.

References

1. Gray H, Standring S. Gray's anatomy: the anatomical basis of clinical practice. Churchill Livingstone; 2008.
2. Hollinshead WH. Anatomy for surgeons. Vol.1 Head and Neck. Hoeber Harper International, Philadelphia, 1966;564-576
3. Devadas D, Pillay M, Sukumaran TT. A cadaveric study on variations in branching pattern of external carotid artery. *Anatomy & cell biology*. 2018 Dec 1;51(4):225-31.
4. Rao TR, Shetty P. Unusual branching pattern of the external carotid artery in a cadaver. *Chang Gung Med J*. 2011 Jan 1;34(6 Suppl):24-7.
5. Heltzel S, Jelinek L, Jaynes D. Variation in the caudal branches of the external carotid artery: comparison of sex and side. *Medical Research Archives*. 2015 Jan 22(1).
6. Michalinos A, Chatzimarkos M, Arkadopoulos N, Safioleas M, Troupis T. Anatomical considerations on surgical anatomy of the carotid bifurcation. *Anatomy Research International*. 2016;2016(1):6907472.
7. Hayashi N, Hori E, Ohtani Y, Ohtani O, Kuwayama N, Endo S. Surgical anatomy of the cervical carotid artery for carotid endarterectomy. *Neurologia medico-chirurgica*. 2005;45(1):25-30.
8. Lučev N, Bobinac D, Marić I, Dreščik I. Variations of the great arteries in the carotid triangle.

- Otolaryngology—Head and Neck Surgery. 2000 Apr;122(4):590-1.
9. Ito H, Mataga I, Kageyama I, Kobayashi K. Clinical anatomy in the neck region-the position of external and internal carotid arteries may be reversed. *Okajimas folia anatomica Japonica*. 2006;82(4):157-68.
 10. Al-Rafiah A, El-Haggagy AA, Aal IH, Zaki AI. Anatomical study of the carotid bifurcation and origin variations of the ascending pharyngeal and superior thyroid arteries. *Folia Morphologica*. 2011;70(1):47-55.
 11. Mompeó B, Bajo E. Carotid bifurcation: clinical relevance. *Eur. j. anat.* 2015 Jan;19(1):37-42.
 12. Lo A, Oehley M, Bartlett A, Adams D, Blyth P, Al-Ali S. Anatomical variations of the common carotid artery bifurcation. *ANZ journal of surgery*. 2006 Nov;76(11):970-2.
 13. Kurkcuoglu A, Aytekin C, Oktem H, Pelin C. Morphological variation of carotid artery bifurcation level in digital angiography. *Folia Morphologica*. 2015;74(2):206-11.
 14. Rielly JP. Intrathoracic carotid bifurcation in Klippel-Feil syndrome. *Journal of vascular surgery*. 2008 May 1;47(5):1071-3.
 15. Gulsen S, Caner H, Altinors N. An anatomical variant: low-lying bifurcation of the common carotid artery, and its surgical implications in anterior cervical discectomy. *Journal of Korean Neurosurgical Society*. 2009 Jan;45(1):32.
 16. Murono S, Nakanishi Y, Minami T, Matsui O, Furukawa M, Yoshizaki T. Intra-arterial chemotherapy for laryngeal cancer via a non-bifurcating carotid artery. *The British Journal of Radiology*. 2009 Oct 1;82(982):e197-9.
 17. Anu VR, Pai MM, Rajalakshmi R, Latha VP, Rajanigandha V, D Costa S. Clinically-relevant variations of the carotid arterial system. *Singapore medical journal*. 2007 Jun 1;48(6):566.
 18. Banna M, Lasjaunias P. The arteries of the lingual thyroid: angiographic findings and anatomic variations. *AJNR: American Journal of Neuroradiology*. 1990 Jul;11(4):730.
 19. Sanjeev IK, Anita H, Ashwini M, Mahesh U, Rairam GB. Branching pattern of external carotid artery in human cadavers. *J Clin Diagn Res*. 2010;4(5):3128-33.
 20. Natsis K, Raikos A, Foundos I, Noussios G, Lazaridis N, Njau SN. Superior thyroid artery origin in Caucasian Greeks: A new classification proposal and review of the literature. *Clinical anatomy*. 2011 Sep;24(6):699-705.
 21. Ovhal AG, Ansari MM, Rajgopal L, Ovhal AG. A cross sectional study of variations in the external carotid artery in cadavers. *Indian Journal of Clinical Anatomy and Physiology*. 2016 Jul;3(3):282-6.
 22. Faller A, Schaerer O. Über die Variabilität der Arteriae thyreoideae. *Cells Tissues Organs*. 1947;4(1-2):119-22.
 23. Quain R. *The anatomy of the arteries of the human body*. Taylor and Walton. 1844.
 24. Tippireddy S, Manikanta Reddy V, Sofia P, Lakshmi Devi C. A Study on the Branching Pattern of External Carotid Artery. *IOSR J. Dent. Med. Sci.* 2019;18:19-22.
 25. Soumya KV. Neurovascular variations in the carotid triangle. *International Journal of Anatomical Variations*. 2008;1:17-8.
 26. Yildrin M, Tanyeli E, Solyluoglu AI, Tuna Y. Truncus linguofacialis siklig. *Morfoloji Der*. 2001;9(1):33-4.

27. Ozgur Z, Govsa F, Ozgur T. Assessment of origin characteristics of the front branches of the external carotid artery. *Journal of Craniofacial Surgery*. 2008 Jul 1;19(4):1159-66.
28. Thwin SS, Soe MM, Myint M, Than M, Lwin S. Variations of the origin and branches of the external carotid artery in a human cadaver. *Singapore Med J*. 2010 Feb 1;51(2):e40-2.
29. Manzato L, Trivelato FP, Alvarenga AY, Rezende MT, Ulhôa AC. Endovascular treatment of a linguofacial trunk pseudoaneurysm after tonsillectomy. *Brazilian Journal of Otorhinolaryngology*. 2013;79:524-.
30. Zümre Ö, Salbacak A, Çiçekcibaşı AE, Tuncer I, Seker M. Investigation of the bifurcation level of the common carotid artery and variations of the branches of the external carotid artery in human fetuses. *Annals of Anatomy-Anatomischer Anzeiger*. 2005 Sep 1;187(4):361-9.
31. Anıl A, Turgut HB, Peker T, Pelin C. Variation of the branches of external carotid artery. *Gazi Medical Journal*. 2000;11(2).
32. Lappas DA, Kamberos SP, GIsakis IG, Takis CH, Lykaki G. Anatomic study of the variations in the origin of the branches of the external carotid artery. *Beta Medical Arts*. 2002;81:28-31.
33. Hayashi N, Hori E, Ohtani Y, Ohtani O, Kuwayama N, Endo S. Surgical anatomy of the cervical carotid artery for carotid endarterectomy. *Neurologia medico-chirurgica*. 2005;45(1):25-30.
34. Shetty SD, Nayak SB, Kumar N, Aithal AP. Low level termination of external carotid artery and its clinical significance: A case report. *Archives of Clinical Experimental Surgery*. 2015;4(3):160-3.
35. Ogeng'o JA, Misiani MK, Loyal P, Ongeti KW, Gimongo J, Inyimili MI, Murunga AK. Variations in branching pattern of external carotid artery in a black Kenyan population. *Anatomy Journal of Africa*. 2015;4(2):584-90.
36. Gluncic V, Petanjek Z, Marusic A, Gluncic I. High bifurcation of common carotid artery, anomalous origin of ascending pharyngeal artery and anomalous branching pattern of external carotid artery. *Surgical and radiologic anatomy*. 2001 Jun;23:123-5.